

Title: Efficient and optimized indexing mechanism of handling small files in Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS)

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INTRODUCTION:

Apache Hadoop is an open source scalable and fault tolerant framework for distributed storing and processing of large sets of data, which can be used on commodity hardware for the cost optimization. It is being open source and driven by flexibility and innovation mainly for unstructured data analysis and store large files. HDFS faces few problems to deal with increased number of small files since the number of files to store in HDFS is constrained by size NameNode's Main memory. Comparative analysis of different methods proposed will be covered as part of this paper and proposing a solution with an improved indexing mechanism.

AIM:

Proposing Improved Indexing mechanism to store small files in HDFS

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Comparative analysis of five methods to deal with small files problem in HDFS

RESULTS:

- Bottlenecks or drawbacks for existing HDFS system
- Comparison of proposed methods to store small files
- Proposing a optimized and improved indexing technique to store data

CONCLUSIONS:

The proposed solution or this paper will be concluded with an improved and efficient indexing technique which reduces the metadata size in NameNode main memory to store small files in the HDFS.

KEYWORDS:

Big Data, HDFS, Small files, indexing,

BIOGRAPHY:

Vinod Nerella completed MS in Management of IT services from School of Management Studies, University at Buffalo, New York and MBA from Amrita School of Business, Bangalore. He is presently working as a Head of Infrastructure in a Dallas based startup Itversity, an IT firm with a primary focus on Big Data. He published multiple papers during his MBA on various aspects.